

FREE-EDGE EFFECT DEVELOPMENT IN THE PROCESSING AND ANNEALING OF FIBRE-REINFORCED SEMICRYSTALLINE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

The residual thermal stresses developed during processing of fibre-reinforced semicrystalline thermoplastic composites are strongly affected by variations in temperature and degree of crystallinity within a laminate. In order to understand the processes at work, a model predicting the temperature and crystallinity volume fraction distributions over the cross-sectional area of these laminates during processing from the melt followed by an annealing cycle has been developed. In this study, emphasis is on the prediction of temperature and crystallinity gradients in the vicinity of free-edges. Results are shown for the case of unidirectional APC-2 laminates.

Keywords : Free-Edge Effect, Thermoplastic, Semicrystalline, Annealing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced composite materials have gained widespread applicability in high performance aerospace structures as a result of their superior specific strength and stiffness. This superiority, however, does not come without trade-offs, which are mainly associated with the matrix and matrix/fibre interfaces. One characteristic of fibre-reinforced composite laminates is their tendency to delaminate under service loading, with failure typically initiating in the vicinity of traction-free-edges¹⁻⁴. Delamination is associated with high interlaminar stresses due to property and geometric discontinuities through-the-thickness at the free edge. Thermoplastic-based composites have given an order of magnitude increase in interlaminar toughness compared to existing epoxy resin composites⁵, increasing their resistance to the initiation of delamination and free-edge failures. However, significant residual thermal stresses at free edges may be developed in thermoplastic composites due to the elevated processing temperatures and the higher matrix/fibre thermal expansion mismatch. These thermally-induced residual stresses may represent a significant fraction of the failure stress of the material, possibly leading to premature failure in the form of delamination and transverse cracking^{6,7}.

Within the class of thermoplastic composites, it is important to distinguish between amorphous and semicrystalline matrices. The high-stiffness crystalline phase in semicrystalline resins contributes to enhanced mechanical properties and superior chemical and radiation resistance when compared to those of the amorphous phase. Levels of crystallinity attained in semicrystalline matrices can be controlled by both the cooling rate applied during processing from the melt, and by the temperature of annealing ("cold crystallization")^{8,9}. Annealing above the glass transition temperature causes an increase in the perfection and the growth of crystalline regions⁹. This process is recommended when cooling rates from the melt have been sufficiently fast to render the matrix at a crystallinity too low to ensure

adequate solvent resistance. As the composite's mechanical properties are dependent on the matrix constituents and the reinforcing phase^{10,11}, the build-up of thermal stresses is directly affected by the variations in temperature and degree of crystallinity within the laminate occurring during both processing⁷ and annealing, and especially in the vicinity of traction free edges.

Several studies have been performed in order to determine the temperature distribution and crystallization kinetics during the processing of thermoplastic-based composites. The majority of these studies model the thermal process using a 1-D heat conduction energy equation through the thickness of the composite^{7,12}, and include a prediction of the degree of crystallinity profile using a crystallization kinetics model coupled to the heat transfer analysis. Both temperature and crystallinity profiles are used to evaluate the mechanical properties of the material necessary for the stress analysis modeling. The abovementioned models emphasize the skin/core (through-the-thickness) distributions, without being able to address the free-edge effect developing during processing.

The model presented in this study is based on a 2-D Heat Transfer analysis over the cross-sectional area of a composite laminate and on a Crystallization Kinetics model, in order to predict the time-dependent temperature and crystallinity profiles during non-isothermal processing from the melt followed by an annealing cycle. In order to elucidate the development of the free-edge effect zone, results are shown for the case of unidirectional APC-2 (graphite-fibre/PEEK) laminates.

2. MODEL DESCRIPTION

2.1. Thermal Analysis

The composite laminate considered for the thermal analysis is a long (infinite) composite strip with finite width and finite thickness. Consequently, the domain modeled is the cross-sectional area of the laminate (Figure 1), where the heat transfer due to conduction and the release of heat caused by the nucleation and growth of crystals are taken into consideration. The analysis requires the simultaneous modeling of temperature and crystallization histories, while the purpose is to determine the complete temperature and crystallinity profiles as a function of position and time.

The thermal analysis is governed by the following 2-D Heat Conduction equation, subjected to the appropriate boundary and initial conditions :

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}[\rho(T)C(T)T] = \nabla \cdot \{K(T)\nabla T\} + U(\dot{X}_{vc}(T)) \quad (1)$$

where t, ρ, T, C, K, U and X_{vc} are the time, density, temperature, specific heat, conductivity matrix, heat release rate per unit volume due to crystallization, and volume fraction crystallinity, respectively. The coupling between the temperature and crystallinity via the term U was found to be relatively weak^{12,13}. Therefore, the temperature distribution can be explicitly calculated from the Heat Conduction equation.

2.2. Crystallization Kinetics Analysis

As mentioned earlier, the crystallization kinetics is modeled because it influences the development of residual stresses and free-edge effect through the mechanical properties of the material. Calculation of the time dependent crystallinity profile is based on the Crystallization Kinetics Model of Velisaris & Seferis¹⁴. The model is based on a linear combination of two crystallization processes (dual mechanism) observed experimentally, and occurring in parallel. The expression for the above-mentioned crystallization kinetics model is given by

$$\frac{X_{vc}}{X_{vc}^{\infty}} = w_1 F_{vc1} + w_2 F_{vc2} \quad (2)$$

where

$$F_{vci} = \left\{ 1 - \exp \left[- \int_0^t k_i(T) n_i t^{n_i-1} dt \right] \right\} \quad ; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (3)$$

$$k_i(T) = C_1 T \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{C_2 i}{T - T_g + 51.6} + \frac{C_3 i}{T(T_{mi} - T)^2} \right] \right\} ; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (4)$$

Here X_{pc}^∞ is the equilibrium volume fraction crystallinity, w_i are weighting factors, C_i are material constants, T_g is the glass transition temperature, T_{mi} are crystal melt temperatures for the dual mechanism, and n_i are Avrami exponents for the dual mechanism. The values used in the present study are reported in [14]. This form of the crystallization equation is only valid for processing starting from the melt (no initial crystallinity). Extension of the model to enable the prediction of degree of crystallinity during an annealing cycle following processing from the melt is presented by Seferis et al.⁸. This extension is given by

$$\ln \left[\frac{1}{1 - F_{vci}} \right]^{1/n_i} = \ln \left[\frac{1}{1 - F_{vci0}} \right]^{1/n_i} + \int_0^t [k_i(T)]^{1/n_i} dt ; \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (5)$$

where F_{vci0} is the normalized initial crystallinity level for the i^{th} mechanism.

The crystallization kinetics in semicrystalline thermoplastics has been shown to be directly related to the cooling rates experienced within the material^{14,15}. As the laminate undergoes large gradients in cooling rates in the vicinity of free-edges, variations in degree of crystallinity are expected within this region. Figure 2 presents the dependence of the volume fraction crystallinity on the cooling rate applied from the melt for APC-2 (graphite-fibre/PEEK) based on the model of Velisaris and Seferis.

2.3. Mechanical Properties Determination

The lamina's mechanical properties required for the stress analysis are strongly dependent on the individual constituent properties, that is on the reinforcing fibres, the matrix crystalline phase and the matrix amorphous phase. Ply properties in both longitudinal and transverse directions are calculated using Micromechanics models, and take into consideration the contribution of the different constituents.

The mechanical properties of the carbon-fibres and the crystalline phase of the PEEK matrix are assumed to exhibit no temperature dependence. The amorphous phase in the PEEK matrix, however, does exhibit a strong dependence on temperature. Consequently, the determination of the time-dependent temperature and crystallinity profiles in the laminate, as calculated from the previous sections, directly influence the development of residual thermal stresses and the free-edge effect through the mechanical properties of the material in both longitudinal and transverse directions.

3. RESULTS

In order to elucidate the development of the free-edge effect zone during the processing from the melt followed by an annealing step in semicrystalline thermoplastic composites, some results describing the transient temperature and crystallinity profiles are presented for the case of unidirectional 16-ply APC-2 (graphite-fibre(AS4)/PEEK) laminates. As previously mentioned, the state of residual thermal stresses and the free-edge effect are directly influenced by these profiles, through the determination of the thermoelastic properties of the material. Results are presented for the horizontal distribution measured from the free-edge.

The temperature and crystallinity profiles developed while processing the laminate from the molten state to room temperature are presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4, respectively, for a surface cooling rate of 35°C/s. As expected, slower cooling rates are experienced at locations away from the free-edge. As the level of crystallinity achieved is strongly dependent upon the cooling rate, significant gradients in degree of crystallinity are obtained during processing in the horizontal direction (Figure 4) as a result of different cooling rates in the free-edge and in the core of the laminate. The free-edge effect appears to vanish totally at a distance of approximately two times the thickness of the laminate. This important observation is compatible with some experimental measurements and numerical results reported by Unger¹⁶ regarding the free-edge zone size in an APC-2 laminate. Unger developed a thermal process for fibre reinforced semicrystalline thermoplastic laminates which reduces the free-edge effect and improves static strength and fatigue life. In this process, referred

to as Localized Reconsolidation, heat and pressure are applied to a laminate's free-edge to locally melt the matrix, and then the region is cooled at a specified rate. A zone of reduced residual stresses was found to be formed, causing a significant improvement in the overall static and fatigue strength. Unger's experimental results prove the observation regarding the size of the free-edge effect region, as no additional improvement was achieved when melting the free-edge beyond a distance of two times the laminate's thickness.

Following the processing from the molten state, the laminate has been exposed to a hypothetical annealing cycle, where the surfaces of the laminate were heated to a specified annealing temperature, kept at this temperature for a specified time, and cooled back to room temperature. Prediction of crystallinity levels during this cycle were based on the model presented in Equations 2 to 5. The temperature and crystallinity development at the free-edge in a laminate cooled at 35°C/s and annealed at 175°C, 225°C and 275°C for 5 minutes is depicted in Figure 5. It can be seen that there is a critical temperature that when annealing above it, a sharp increase in degree of crystallinity occurs for a short period of time followed by an almost constant level. The value of this critical temperature is approximately 180°C, and is compatible with results reported in [16]. Therefore, annealing above this critical temperature will result in a significant addition of crystallinity to laminates that were cooled from the melt at rates that resulted in a low-crystallinity matrix.

The temperature and crystallinity distributions measured from the free-edge are shown in Figure 6 to Figure 8 for the same aforementioned annealing temperatures. As observed in the case of processing from the melt, the influence of the free-edge during the annealing cycle appears to vanish at a distance of two laminate thicknesses. However, it is very important to notice from Figure 7 and Figure 8 that, as a result of annealing at a temperature higher than the critical temperature, an uniform crystallinity distribution is achieved within the laminate. This behavior leads to the alteration of the residual thermal stresses in the vicinity of the free-edge when compared to the stresses state resulted from the regular processing of cooling from the melt.

At this point it is important to remember that the residual thermal stress state is strongly affected by the temperature and crystallinity gradients occurring during the thermal process, and *not only* by the steady-state levels achieved at the end of the process⁷. Therefore, the results shown in the present study emphasize the importance of the prediction of free-edge singularities developing during processing and annealing of semicrystalline thermoplastic composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A model which predicts the temperature and volume fraction crystallinity distributions in the cross-sectional area of a semicrystalline thermoplastic laminate during processing from the melt followed by an annealing cycle is presented. The model enables the prediction of free-edge effects developing during these thermal processes.

Processing from the melt at fast cooling rates may lead to significant crystallinity gradients in the vicinity of the free-edge. This effect seems to vanish at a distance of two laminate thicknesses from the free-edge. Following processing from the melt, application of an annealing cycle above a critical temperature of approximately 180°C will result in a uniform crystallinity distribution between the free-edge and the interior of the laminate, leading to the alteration of the residual thermal stress state.

As the residual stress state is strongly affected by the *temperature and crystallinity gradients occurring during processing* (and not only by the steady-state levels) through changes in mechanical properties, the results emphasize the importance of the prediction of free-edge singularities developing during the processing and annealing of fibre-reinforced semicrystalline thermoplastic composites.

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Figure 1. 2-D space domain of the problem.

Figure 2. Volume Fraction Crystallinity vs. Cooling Rate for APC-2 (model of Velisaris & Seferis¹⁷).

Figure 3. Horizontal temperature distribution at various times for a 16-Ply U-D APC-2 laminate cooled at 35°C/s.

Figure 4. Horizontal crystallinity distribution at various times for a 16-Ply U-D APC-2 laminate cooled at 35°C/s.

Figure 5. Temperature and crystallinity development at the free-edge in APC-2 cooled at 35°C/s and annealed for 5 minutes at various temperatures.

Figure 6. Horizontal crystallinity distribution at various times for a 16-Ply U-D APC-2 laminate cooled at 35°C/s and annealed at 175°C for 5 minutes.

Figure 7. Horizontal crystallinity distribution at various times for a 16-Ply U-D APC-2 laminate cooled at 35⁰C/s and annealed at 225⁰C for 5 minutes.

Figure 8. Horizontal crystallinity distribution at various times for a 16-Ply U-D APC-2 laminate cooled at 35⁰C/s and annealed at 275⁰C for 5 minutes.